

Seasonal distribution of rice stem borers in the Mekong Delta of Vietnam

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After the brown planthopper, the stem borer is the most destructive insect pest of rice in the Mekong Delta. Studies of the population dynamics of major insect pests of rice by the Plant Protection Department showed that *Tryporyza incertulas* was the most damaging of the four stem borer species in the area and *Chilo polychrysus* was second. From the beginning of the rainy season, at the early vegetative stage of the 1978 summer-autumn crop, *C. polychrysus* comprised 95% of the stem borer population at Cho Gao, a high yielding area of Tien Giang Province (Table 1). *Tryporyza incertulas* then gradually assumed predominance from the flowering stage of this crop (Table 2) and completely predominated later in the local crop (Jul–Dec) and winter-spring crop 1978–79 (86% of the population at Chau Thanh, Ben Tre Province and 96% of that at Cho Moi, An Giang Province.

The data show that competition for host plants between these predominant species is high. *Chilo polychrysus* apparently prefers the low water level of

Table 1. Distribution of stem borer^a species in some high-yielding areas of the Mekong Delta of Vietnam.

Location	Distribution (%)			
	<i>Chilo polychrysus</i>	<i>Tryporyza incertulas</i>	<i>Chilo suppressalis</i>	<i>Sesamia inferens</i>
<i>1978 summer-autumn crop</i>				
Cho Gao, Tien Giang	95	5	0	0
Phu Tan, An Giang	48	31	16	6
<i>1978-79 winter-spring crop</i>				
Cho Gao, Tien Giang	20	54	15	11
Cho Moi, An Giang	0	96	0	4
Chau Thanh, Ben Tre	4	86	0	10
Chau Thanh, Hau Giang	32	51	0	17

^a Mean of 100 larvae found by dissecting infested plants at 30–40 days after transplanting.

Table 2. Distribution of stem borer^a species at 2 different stages of the 1978 summer-autumn crop and 1978-79 winter-spring crop. Mekong Delta, Vietnam.

Growth stage ^b	Distribution (%)			
	<i>Chilo polychrysus</i>	<i>Tryporyza incertulas</i>	<i>Chilo suppressalis</i>	<i>Sesamia inferens</i>
<i>1978 summer-autumn crop</i>				
40 DT	90	8	1	0
70 DT	22	66	5	7
<i>1978-79 winter-spring crop</i>				
40 DT	0	96	0	4
70 DT	50	26	11	14

^a Mean of 100 larvae found by dissecting infested plants at 40 and 70 days after transplanting. ^b DT = days after transplanting.

rice fields at the beginning of the rainy season and, because of its gregarious living habit, cannot tolerate the high rainfall and deep water that occur later.

Tryporyza incertulas can even live below the water level but because it cannot stand dryness, it takes over in areas of local and deepwater rice. ■

A spray volume calculation chart for 19-, 16-, and 10-liter capacity knapsack sprayers

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Spraying is the most common method Asian rice farmers use to apply insecticides. Knapsack sprayers with 19-, 16-, or 10-liter capacities are popular. Good insect control can be achieved with contact or stomach poisons if rice foliage is covered by the spray solution.

Spraying rice is time-consuming and laborious, and requires much water. In irrigated rice areas, water is usually available in the rice field or from nearby canals. But in rainfed areas, a water

source may be far away, and refilling may require many trips. Dosage calculations have been based on 1,000-liters/ha, a spray volume often stipulated in insecticide recommendations.

Recent IRRI studies, however, have shown that the stipulated amount is unrealistically high. For each application, farmers spraying 1 ha would have to refill their 19-, 16-, and 10-liter sprayers 53, 63, and 100 times, respectively. Farmers rarely do that and it is unnecessary. For example, excellent brown planthopper control can be achieved at booting with perthane sprayed at the low volume of 190 liters/ha.

But for safety, farmers are advised to apply 300–500 liters/ha to further dilute the insecticide spray. Low spray

volumes (300 liters/ha) are adequate when rice plants are small (before maximum tillering) but volumes must be higher (500 liters/ha) when the rice canopy has closed.

Spray-volume calculation requires knowledge of the field area, sprayer capacity, and number of sprayerloads per field. Farmers generally possess such knowledge and a chart has been developed for use by extension workers in helping farmers improve their proficiency in insecticide application.

The following formula is used to determine the spray volume in liters per hectare:

$$\text{No. of sprayerloads per field} \times \frac{\text{sprayer capacity (liters)}}{\text{area of field (ha)}} = \text{spray volume (liters/ha)}$$